

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Title of Survey: Knowledge Gaps and Predictors of Mpox Awareness Among Undergraduate Health Sciences Students in Ghana: A Cross-Sectional Study

Principal Investigator:

Mr. Christopher Yaw Dumevi

Department of Physician Assistantship Studies, School of Medical Sciences, Central University, Tema, Ghana

Tel: +233243277804

Email: cdumevi@central.edu.gh or chrisdumevi@gmail.com

Ethics Approval

This study has received ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board Institutional Review Board of Central University, Accra, Ghana, Approval No. CUIRB/21/03/24, dated March 1, 2024.

1. Introduction

I, Christopher Yaw Dumevi, of the School of Medical Sciences, Central University, Accra, kindly invite you to participate in the above-mentioned research study. This document explains the purpose of the study, any potential risks and benefits, and your rights as a participant. Please read it carefully before deciding whether to take part.

2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the level of knowledge and perceptions regarding Mpox among undergraduate health sciences students specifically those studying Nursing, Public Health, Pharmacy, and Physician Assistantship Studies at Central University, Accra, Ghana. Data collection is anticipated to take place from March 2024 to May 2024. A structured questionnaire will collect sociodemographic data and assess knowledge across seven thematic areas: general knowledge, aetiology, transmission, One Health concept, epidemiology, signs and symptoms, and prevention. Additional items will evaluate perceptions regarding Mpox.

3. Voluntary Participation and Right to Withdraw

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. You may decide not to take part, or you may withdraw at any time without giving a reason. If you withdraw, any data collected up to that point will be deleted upon your request and will not be used in the analysis. Refusal to participate or withdrawal will **not** affect your academic standing, grades, tuition quality, or any services provided by your department or Central University.

4. Possible Risks and Discomforts

There are no physical risks associated with this survey. The only possible minor discomfort is the time required; approximately 10–15 minutes to complete the questionnaire accurately and independently.

5. Possible Benefits

While there may be no direct personal benefit, your participation will help us understand Mpox knowledge gaps among health sciences students in Ghana. This may inform future educational interventions and contribute to outbreak preparedness. You will also have the opportunity to reflect on your own knowledge of this emerging infectious disease.

6. Alternatives to Participation

Participation is entirely voluntary. The alternative to taking part is simply not to participate. No other alternatives exist for this survey-based study.

7. Termination of Participation by the Researcher

This is not applicable to this study. There are no circumstances under which the researcher will terminate a participant's involvement without the participant's consent.

8. Notification of Significant New Findings

This is not applicable. Because data collection is a single, anonymous survey with no follow-up, no significant new findings will arise during the study that would affect a participant's willingness to continue.

9. Compensation and Costs

There is no financial compensation or reimbursement for participation, and there are no costs to you.

10. Confidentiality and Data Protection

All data collected will be **anonymised** immediately using unique participant codes. No names or identifying information will appear in any publication, report, or presentation. The Central University Institutional Review Board (CU-IRB) and authorised auditors may have access to anonymised research records for the purpose of ethical oversight.

Data will be stored on a password-protected computer accessible only to the principal investigator. Hard copies (if any) will be kept in a locked cabinet. Identifiable information (e.g., signed consent forms) will be retained separately and destroyed after 5 years. Your individual responses will never be traceable back to you.

Your data will be processed in accordance with the Ghana Data Protection Act, 2012 (Act 843) and applicable research ethics guidelines.

11. Feedback and Access to Results

If you wish to receive a summary of the study findings, you may contact the principal investigator at cdumevi@central.edu.gh after October 2025. Individual requests for your own data will be verified against signed consent forms before release.

12. Right to Complain / Contact for Institutional Review Board

No research-related injury is anticipated. If you nevertheless experience any distress, please contact the principal investigator or the CU-IRB. If you have any concerns about your rights as a research participant, please contact the Institutional Review Board at:

cuirb@central.edu.gh Telephone: Telephone: (+233) 0533 980 310 / +233 0303 318580 / +233 0303 318588

For concerns related to the study conduct, you may contact:

- **Lead Supervisor:** Rev. Prof. Patrick Ferdinand Ayeh-Kumi
Tel: +233244042718 | Email: pfayeh-kumi@ug.edu.gh

Medical Microbiology Department, University of Ghana Medical School

- **Co-Investigator:** Ezekiel Kofi Vicar
Tel: +233242617962 | Email: ekvicar@uds.edu.gh

Department of Clinical Microbiology, School of Medicine, University for Development Studies, Tamale, Ghana

- **Co-Investigator:** Francis Medodzi Amesinu
Tel: +233243494871 | Email: francis.medodzi.amesinu23@central.edu.gh

Department of Nursing, School of Nursing and Midwifery, Central University, Tema, Ghana

13. Funding

This study is self-funded by the principal investigator. The investigators declare no conflicts of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

STUDY TITLE: Knowledge Gaps and Predictors of Mpox Awareness Among Undergraduate Health Sciences Students in Ghana: A Cross-Sectional Study

PARTICIPANT’S STATEMENT OF CONSENT

I confirm that:

- 1. I have read the Participant Information Sheet or it has been read and explained to me in English, which I understand).
- 2. I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and all questions have been answered to my satisfaction.
- 3. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw at any time without giving a reason and without any consequence to my academic standing.
- 4. I understand that my data will be anonymised and kept confidential, and that no identifying information will be published.
- 5. I understand who to contact if I have concerns about my rights as a participant.

I voluntarily agree to take part in this research.

- A. I agree to participate
- B. I do not agree to participate (*if selected, do not sign below*)

Name of Participant (print):

Participant’s Signature: **OR Thumb Print:**

Date:

INTERPRETER’S STATEMENT (if applicable)

I have interpreted the purpose and contents of the Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form to the above-named participant in English to the best of my ability. All questions raised by the participant have been interpreted and answered to their satisfaction.

Name of Interpreter (print):

Signature of Interpreter: (*thumb print not required*)

Date:

WITNESS STATEMENT (if consent was read/explained to a non-literate participant)

I was present when the purpose and contents of the Participant Information Sheet were read and explained to the participant in a language they understand (English). The participant was given the opportunity to ask questions, and all questions were answered to their satisfaction. They voluntarily agreed to take part.

Name of Witness (print):

Signature of Witness: (*thumb print not required*)

Date:

INVESTIGATOR'S STATEMENT

I certify that the participant has been given ample time to read and understand the information about the study. All questions and clarifications raised by the participant have been addressed.

Researcher's Name (print):

Researcher's Signature:

Date:

PROVISION OF DOCUMENTS

A signed copy of this Information Sheet and Consent Form will be given to you to keep.